

Parameter optimisation of combined pyrolysis and oxidation for recycling of CFRP composites

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The predicted amount of wasted carbon fibre:
10000t in 2005 --- 57,000t in 2010 --- 88,000t in 2015 --- 130,000t in 2020
--- 263,000t in 2030 ^[1]

- ❑ Establishing a closed-loop life cycle for CFRP composites is crucial to protect our environment and to maximise material utilisation and energy efficiency.

- Minimise the amount of CFRP waste sent to landfill
- Reduce non-renewable energy consumption
- Minimise the green house effect
- expand the material options for ‘green engineering’ which is defined as building with fewer negative effects on the natural environment, society and human health
- Revitalise the economic value of carbon fibre in composites
- Reduce the cost for FRP manufacturing
- More suited for medium and even small-sized businesses, as equipment and operating costs will be reduced compared to existing methods

Considering NPV and BCR analysis results for CFRP recycling methods, pyrolysis combined with oxidation could achieve greatest profitability rate with lower expenditure (i.e. higher BCR) while alkali solvolysis can achieve the highest total net profit value with higher expenditure^[2].

Arrhenius-type kinetic analysis and FRP thermal degradation mechanisms

Coats-Redfern method

$$\ln \frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} = \ln \left[\frac{AR}{\beta E} \left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right) \right] - \frac{E}{RT}$$

Coats-Redfern method

model-fitting method

- Discover the effects caused by changing heating rate
- More accurate result for the specific heating condition

Friedman method $n \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) = \ln \left(\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT} \right) = \ln [A(1-\alpha)^n] - \frac{E}{RT}$ OFW method $\ln \beta = \ln \left(\frac{AE}{Rg(\alpha)} \right) - 5.331 - 1.052 \frac{E}{RT}$
KAS method $\ln \frac{\beta}{T^2} = \ln \left(\frac{AR}{Eg(\alpha)} \right) - \frac{E}{RT}$ Straink method $\ln \left(\frac{\beta}{T^{1.92}} \right) = -1.0008 \frac{E}{RT} + C$

Friedman method; OFW method
KAS method; Straink method

model-free methods

- Simplify investigation process
- Reduce the assumption errors made before operating the experiments

VS

Trendline parameters (slope, a, and x-interception, b) and R² values correspond to conversion fractions in Friedman method

Conversion Fraction, α	For figure (c)		
	a (×10 ⁴)	b	R ²
0.1	-1.90	23.78	0.85
0.2	-2.15	27.85	0.74
0.3	-2.16	27.88	0.79
0.4	-2.53	33.03	0.71
0.5	-3.10	40.32	0.58
0.9	-5.12	44.40	1.00

Friedman method

$$\ln\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right) = \ln\left(\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right) = \ln[A(1-\alpha)^n] - \frac{E}{RT}$$

(a) $\ln(\beta d\alpha/dT)$ versus $1/T$, (b) lining up the data for three heating rates for the same conversion fraction (α), (c) determining the slope of regression line for each conversion (values of a, b and R² are shown in Table 2), (d) Friedman method result: activation energies at different conversions.

(a and b) Results derived from OFW and (c and d) KAS method; (a and c) $\text{Ln}(\beta/T^2)$ versus $1/T$, and (b and d) regression lines corresponding to each conversion fraction (values of a , b and R^2 are shown in Table 2).

Trendline parameters (slope, a , and x -interception, b) and R^2 values correspond to conversion fractions in KAS method

Conversion Fraction, α	For figure (d)		
	a ($\times 10^4$)	b	R^2
0.1	-2.16	18.26	0.54
0.2	-1.86	14.27	0.66
0.3	-1.72	12.47	0.71
0.4	-1.61	11.17	0.75
0.5	-1.27	6.52	0.88
0.9	-2.89	14.21	0.76

OFW method

$$\ln \beta = \ln \left(\frac{AE}{Rg(\alpha)} \right) - 5.331 - 1.052 \frac{E}{RT}$$

KAS method

$$\ln \frac{\beta}{T^2} = \ln \left(\frac{AR}{Eg(\alpha)} \right) - \frac{E}{RT}$$

Starink method

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T^{1.92}}\right) = -1.0008 \frac{E}{RT} + C$$

- Starink method follows the same approach as that of KAS method but redefines the preliminary assumption of E/RT_f based on the experimental results of solid-state thermal decomposition reaction.
- This approximation results in the adjustment of exponent parameter of T from 2 to 1.92, which can be reflected in curve lifting of $\ln(\beta/T^x)$ versus $1/T$.
- This modification can provide more accurate result for FRP composite decomposition kinetics.

Developing a CFRP thermal degradation process via parameter optimisation
and investigating the properties of recycled carbon fibres

CFRP Recycling

Selection of the pre-treatment medium based on kinetic behavior and mechanical properties of recovered fibres

CH₃COOH

NaOH

H₂SO₄

CFRP Recycling

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

SEM images of fibres recovered with different pre-treatments: (a) and (b) for heating up to 80 °C with 60 mins isothermal dwelling time, (c) and (d) for heating up to 100 °C without isothermal dwelling time

The strength of the recycled fibres was preserved at over 90% of their virgin state, which is 10.21% higher than the strength of recycled fibres recovered via thermal degradation only.

Practical Application

Recovered carbon fibre from (a) and (c) bike fork with coating and (b) and (d) bike fork without coating (coating removed via fine graded polishing) prior to recycling process

Average tensile strength and tensile modulus of different recycled fibres

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Tensile strength (a and c) and modulus (b and d) of recovered fibres from airplane wastes, and (e and f) SEM images with magnification of (e) $\times 1500$ and (f) $\times 3000$

Conclusions

- A closed-loop CFRP life cycle can reduce pollution by decreasing waste disposal, maximise material use and save energy. This contributes to the circular economy and environmental protection.
- To optimise CFRP composite recycling, energy consumption, kinetic behaviour and thermal degradation mechanism during pyrolysis were studied.
- The proposed recycling procedure includes solvolysis pre-treatment of CFRP at 100 °C, followed by pyrolysis up to 425 °C and oxidation up to 550 °C with a heating rate of 15 °C /min.
- Additional solvolysis procedure can increase retention of fibre's mechanical properties by decreasing heat consumption during recycling. When proper pre-treatment was used prior to thermal deterioration, the strength of recycled fibres can be preserved at over 90% of their virgin state.
- By putting this technology in practise, the results of recycling bicycle and aircraft components demonstrated that the parameters must be slightly altered for various types of CFRP based on the matrix type. In addition, the coating should be thoroughly removed from the components prior to waste recycling to prevent major fibre damage during the polishing process.

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